

ASSESSMENT OF THE NUTRITIONAL AND HEALTH BENEFITS OF CHRYSOPHYLLUM ALBIDUM (CHERRY) IN ONDO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE

Olarewaju, Cecilia Abiodun, Ph.D

Department of Home Economics,
Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo
+2348036792393, cecilia_abiodun@yahoo.co.uk

Abstract

Cherry is loaded with various nutritional and health benefits. It lowers blood sugar and cholesterol and also helps in the prevention of heart diseases. This research work was carried out to assess the nutritional and health benefits of Chrysophyllum albidum (Cherry) in Ondo West Local Government Area (OWLGA) of Ondo State. The study considered the fruits, seeds, leaves, bark and roots of cherry. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. A total sample of one hundred and eighty (180) respondents (0.14% of the population of adults in OWLGA) was selected for the study. A four-point likert scale type structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. The data was analyzed using frequency count, percentages and mean scores. Major findings revealed that most respondents (with a mean above 2.5 cut-off) believed that Cherry can be used in preventing some diseases like sore throat and eye problem. Contrary to previous literature works, many of the respondents (with a mean above 2.5) did not agree that Cherry is a good source of Iron and therefore cannot be used to treat anemia. Respondents have little knowledge on how best to preserve the fruit for future use especially when out of season. It was recommended that the populace especially mothers should be sensitized on the importance of the fruit so that they can incorporate it into their food menu when it is in season. Nutritionists and health workers should be encouraged to recommend this fruit for anemic patients and also make use of other parts of the plant in treating diseases.

Keywords: *Cherry, Ondo West, Health, Nutritional benefit*

Introduction

Generally, fruits provide essential vitamins, fibers and other substances that are important for good health. Most fruits are naturally low in fat and calories and are filling. *Chrysophyllum* is a group of trees in the Sapotaceae described as a genus by Linnaeus (1753). The genus is native to tropical regions throughout the world with the greatest number of species in northern South America. Some examples of the species are *Chrysophyllum africanum*, *Chrysophyllum albidum*, *Chrysophyllum beguei*, *Chrysophyllum giganteum*, *Chrysophyllum cuneifolium*, *Chrysophyllum manaosense* and so on. The common species throughout the Central, East and West Africa tropical regions is the *Chrysophyllum albidum*. It is primarily a forest tree and its natural occurrences have been reported in diverse zones in Nigeria, Uganda, Niger Republic, Cameroon and Cote d'ivoire (Bada, 1997). The plant has, in recent times, become a crop of commercial value in Nigeria (Oboh, Aluyor & Audu, 2009). It is known for its sweet edible fruits and various ethano-medical uses. The plant is known as *Agbalumo* in Yoruba language and *Udara* in Igbo language. It is the Nigeria's own local "cherry" as opined by Bada (1997). It is also known and referred to as "The African Star Apple".

When ripe, the fruit has a tender, sweet and tart tasting inner flush which is dark red/orange in colour; it possesses a cluster of about 5 large seeds stuck together in the shape of a star. The seeds have a shiny hard brown casing which feels like plastic and are covered with a creamish-white fibrous sweet membrane. It is considered a super fruit because of the health benefits attached to it. This fruit, though also found in urban areas, is predominantly cultivated in rural areas with harvest falling between the months of December and April. Traditionally, the fruits are not harvested from the trees, but left to drop naturally to the forest floor where they are picked up (Amusa, Ashaye & Oladapo, 2003).

The cherry has a good number of health benefits. It lowers blood sugar and cholesterol and helps in the prevention and treatment of heart diseases. It also has an anti-plasmodia effect (Adewoye, Salami & Taiwo, 2003). The fleshy pulp of the fruit is eaten especially as snacks and has been found to have a very high content of ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) with 1,000mg to 3,300mg

of ascorbic acid per 100g of edible fruit or about 100 times that of oranges and 10 times that of guava or cashew (Amusa *et al.*, 2003). It is also reported as an excellent source of vitamins, iron and flavours to diets (Adisa, 2000). The seeds are either used for local game or discarded (Bada, 1997). In recent times, children in schools use dried Cherry seeds as counters in mathematics lessons. The high content of vitamin C helps prevent scurvy, a disease of gums, bones and blood vessels, and increases the body's resistance to infections. Several other components of the tree including the roots and leaves are reportedly used for medicinal purposes. For example, diseases like malaria, yellow fever, skin eruption, stomach ache and diarrhea can be treated with the bark of this plant. The leaves are used as emollient and for the treatment of skin eruptions, diarrhea and stomach aches, which occur as a result of infections and inflammatory reactions (Adisa, 2000). The people of south western Nigeria have been using *C. albidum* leaves for the management of infections.

The fruit serves as a good source of calcium, with each serving providing an individual with 10% of the daily requirement (Ignatius, 2007). The calcium lends strength to human bones and teeth and may also lessen symptoms of pre-menstrual syndrome, such as cramping and abdominal bloating (Ignatius, 2007). There are many medicinal benefits to derive from the use of the entire plant of Cherry. Most people only take the fruit not for the health benefit they stand to gain but its taste alone. There is, therefore, need for people to be enlightened on the various nutritional benefits of this fruit and plant in its entirety.

Failure to make people understand the usefulness of this plant will amount to wastage of resources. The plant will also remain among the underutilized plants in this part of the world. Also, according to various researchers, various parts of this plant has multi-dimensional use in curing many common ailments like malaria, sore throat, stomach upset, diarrhea, and so on. The knowledge people have will enable them to easily make use of this plant to treat themselves of these commonly occurring ailments.

Assessment on the benefits of *Chrysophyllum albidum* (Cherry) may be of help in increasing its planting, processing, marketing and consumption. Various stages in the planting, processing and marketing will provide job for job seekers and help

in improving the economy of the country. The purpose of this study was to determine the nutritional and health benefits of *Chrysophyllum albidum* in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State (OWLGA). Specifically, the study determined the residents of OWLGAs knowledge on:

- i. the awareness of nutritional and health benefits of Cherry
- ii. the usage of different parts of Cherry
- iii. the storage pattern of the fruit of Cherry

The following research questions guided the study.

- i. Do residents of OWLGA have knowledge of nutritional and health benefits of the Cherry?
- ii. Do they have the knowledge of the pattern of usage of the different parts of the Cherry plant?
- iii. How do they store the Cherry fruit in the above name area?

Method

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The area for this research work was Ondo West Local Government Area (OWLGA). OWLGA is one of the eighteen Local Government Areas in Ondo State of Nigeria. It has an area of 970km² and made up of twelve (12) wards (National Commission of Nigeria Census, NPC 2006).

Ondo West Local Government Area has a population of two hundred and eighty-three thousand, six hundred and seventy-two (283,672) (NPC, 2006). This population which consisted of adults both literates and non-literates, is distributed among the twelve wards of Ondo West Local Government Area.

A total of one hundred and eighty (180) (0.14% of the total population of adults in OWLGA) was selected by systematic random sampling technique from six wards selected out of the available twelve wards by balloting.

A structured questionnaire was used to carry out the study. The questionnaire consisted of four sections. The first section (Section A) consisted of the personal data of the respondents. Section B consisted of the nutritional and health benefits of the Cherry. Section C consisted of the plant parts used in Ondo West Local Government Area. Section D consisted of information on the storage and preservation pattern of the fruit.

The instrument for data collection was subjected to face and content validity by three experts in Food and Nutrition to ascertain whether the instrument elicited responses and information required within the framework of the research objectives.

One hundred and eighty (180) copies of questionnaire were produced in order to get the information needed for the study. The researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents with the help of trained research assistants. The non-literate residents were assisted in the interpretation and filling of the items by the researcher and the research assistants. The completed copies were collected immediately by hand.

The following data analysis techniques was used and interpreted.

- i. Frequency counts and percentage
- ii. Mean scores (\bar{x}): The mean scores of the questionnaire items were interpreted based on the statistical real limits of the numbers as follows:

<i>Response Category Boundary</i>	<i>Points</i>	<i>Limits</i>
Strongly Agree (S.A)	4	3.00 – 4.49
Agree (A)	3	2.50 – 2.99
Strongly Disagree (S.D)	2	1.50 – 2.49
Disagree (D)	1	0.50 – 1.49

2.50 was the cut-off point accepted as agreed

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Awareness of respondents on the nutritional and health benefits of Cherry

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	Remark
1.	Cherry cannot be used in preventing some diseases	2.4	Disagree
2.	The fruit is a good source of calcium, with each serving providing 10% of individual daily needs	3.1	Agree
3.	The fruit is not a good source of Vitamin C	1.9	Disagree
4.	Eating up to 3-5 fruits can give a feeling of being full, can therefore help to control food intake and manage weight	2.9	Agree
5.	The pulp contains greater amount of crude fibre, fat and caloric value	2.7	Agree
6.	The peel contains lesser amount of moisture than pulp and seed	2.8	Agree
7.	Carbohydrate content and crude protein is higher in the seed than the peel and pulp	2.6	Agree
8.	Pulp has greater amount of sodium and iron than the peel	2.8	Agree
9.	Peel contains greater amount of potassium and zinc than the pulp	2.8	Agree
10.	Calcium and magnesium are higher in the seed than pulp and peel	2.7	Agree
11.	Cherry is not an excellent source of Iron	2.6	Agree
12.	Cherry is a good source of fat which the body requires for energy and metabolism	2.7	Agree

The data presented in the table shows that the mean response for items 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 were 3.1, 2.9, 2.7, 2.8, 2.6, 2.8, 2.8, 2.7, 2.6, and 2.7 respectively which simply means that the respondents agreed with the items while items 1 and 3 with mean response of 2.4 and 1.9 shows that the respondents disagreed with the items.

Table 2: Responses on the knowledge of usage pattern of the parts of Cherry

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	Remark
1.	The seed is not useful in the preparation of medicines for the treatment of loss or absence of menstrual cycle in women	2.5	Agree
2.	The leaves of Cherry boiled with sliced fruits of citrus lemon can treat malaria	3.2	Agree
3.	When the seed of Cherry is grinded and mixed with Palm Oil, it can cure haemorrhoids (piles)	3.0	Agree
4.	The root of the Cherry plant together with Shea butter is able to cure cough	3.0	Agree
5.	The fresh fruit eaten directly cannot cure Vitamin deficiencies	2.2	Disagree
6.	The immature fruit mixed with alcohol can relief dental decay	2.8	Agree
7.	The leaves of Cherry boiled with Helitropiumindicum (cock's comb - OgbeAkuko plant can cure blood pressure	2.9	Agree
8.	Boiled leaves of Cherry cannot treat anaemia (low blood level)	2.4	Disagree
9.	The root of Cherry boiled with the leaves is able to treat small pox	2.8	Agree
10.	The root added with fermented water from maize can cure sexual weakness	2.9	Agree

The data presented in table 2 above shows that the mean response for items 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9 and 10 were 2.5, 3.2, 3.0, 3.0, 2.8, 2.9, 2.8, and 2.9 respectively which simply means that the respondents agreed with the items while items 6 and 9 with mean response of 2.2 and 2.4 showed that the respondents disagreed with the items.

Table 3: Responses on the knowledge of storage pattern of Cherry fruit

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	Remark
1.	Cherry can be stored in the refrigerator	3.2	Agree
2.	Cherry cannot be stored under the shade	2.4	Disagree
3.	The juice can be preserved in the refrigerator for a long time	3.0	Agree
4.	The fruits can be wrapped into the leaves for storage	2.9	Agree
5.	The peeled fruit cannot be stored in sugar syrup	2.5	Agree
6.	The moisture content of the peel of Cherry is widely used in food processing	2.7	Agree
7.	The low moisture content of the seed enables easy processing and preservation	2.8	Agree
8.	The preservation of Cherry cannot be done domestically thereby cannot provide cheap method of preservation.	2.5	Agree

The data presented in table 3 shows that the mean response for items 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 with the mean response of 3.2, 3.0, 2.9, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8 and 2.5 respectively which simply means that the respondents agreed with the items while item 2 with mean response of 2.4 shows that the respondents disagreed with the item.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis in shows that majority of the respondents agreed that Cherry can be used in preventing some diseases and that it is a good source of calcium, fibre, fat, protein, potassium and zinc. This result is in tandem with Ignatius (2007) and Amusa *et al.* (2003) that Cherry serves as a good source of calcium and it is an excellent source of vitamins such as A and C. As well, majority of the respondents agreed that Cherry is not an excellent source of iron that corroborates Amusa *et al's* (2003) opinion that Cherry (African Star Apple) serves up to 20% of iron, a mineral vital for oxygenating the body and is needed every day.

Also, the respondents agreed that the leaves of Cherry can treat malaria which is in agreement with Houessau, Lougbegno, Gbesso, Anagonou and Brice's (2012) observation that the leaves of Cherry boiled with sliced fruits of citrus lemon can treat malaria. However, respondents disagreed that boiled leaves of Cherry cannot treat anaemia as against the observation of Houessou *et al* (2012) that the boiled dried leaves of Cherry can cure anaemia.

Respondents agreed that Cherry can be stored in the refrigerator, under the shade, and wrapped into leaves. The finding does not support the statement of Adindu, Williams and Adiele (2003) that the shelf-life of Cherry was delayed longest in the refrigerator followed by being stored in the shade and covering with its leaves. However, the respondents agreed with the statement that the peeled fruit of Cherry can be stored in sugar syrups in tandem with the opinion of Adesina and Aina (2000) that the peeled fruit of Cherry can be stored in sugar syrups either with or without metabisulphate or sorbate. In addition, majority of the respondents agreed with the statement that the preservation of Cherry cannot be done domestically. This finding supports the opinion of Adindu *et al.* (2003) and Adesina and Aina (2000) that Cherry can be stored under the shade and wrapped into leaves or perforated polythene which can be referred to as domestic and cheap method of storage of Cherry.

Conclusion

This study concludes that *Chrysophyllum albidum* commonly referred to as Cherry in Nigeria is known virtually by the residents of OWLGA in Ondo State. Yet, the knowledge of usage pattern of this plant is very low among people of Ondo West Local Government. Most people do not have the idea of how best they can preserve the proceeds (fruits) of the plants especially the fruits.

Recommendations

There is greatest problem of availability, awareness of people and storage which needs to be improved. The researcher therefore, recommends as follows:

1. The populace should be made to realize the importance of this fruit especially mothers so that they can incorporate it into their food menu when it is in season.
2. Nutritionists can also be of great help in creating awareness of the nutritional benefits of Cherry as they are involved in planning meals for people
3. Health workers should be encouraged to recommend this fruit for patients and also make use of other parts of the plant in treating diseases
4. The media houses such as radio and television should help in sensitizing the populace on the usefulness of the various nutrients embedded in the fruit and various health challenges that Cherry can help to eradicate.

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